

A confirmatory factor analyses of the order-processing questionnaire: A potential tool for detecting early mathematical difficulties

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The Order-Processing Questionnaire (OPQ) is a brief parental-report measure designed to assess children's everyday ordering skills, which have been linked to early mathematical development. This study aimed to validate the OPQ's two-factor structure, previously identified by O'Connor et al. (2018), using confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) in a larger sample. Parents of 509 children in their first year of primary school in Northern Ireland completed the OPQ online. CFA tested the original two-factor model comprising positively and negatively worded items. Model fit was mixed: while indices such as the Comparative Fit Index (CFI) and Standardised Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) indicated adequate fit (i.e. the analysis provides a reasonable representation of the patterns in the data), the Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) and chi-square test suggested poorer fit (i.e. analysis does not capture those patterns in the data well). Factor loadings were moderate to strong, and internal consistency was acceptable for the Positive Item factor but weaker for the Negative Item factor, likely reflecting the smaller number of negatively worded items. Evidence of discriminant validity was observed, although convergent validity was stronger for the Positive Item factor. These findings provide partial support for the OPQ's two-factor structure but highlight the need for refinement, particularly regarding negatively phrased items. The study underscores the OPQ's potential as a non-invasive tool for identifying children at risk of early mathematical difficulties while recommending further work to improve its psychometric properties and examine predictive validity. Incorporating socioeconomic status measures and multi-informant reports in future studies will strengthen the OPQ's utility as a screening instrument to support early identification and intervention in educational settings.

Keywords: development; factor analysis; mathematics; ordinality; questionnaire

Early mathematics and reading skills serve as essential foundations for future academic achievement and broader life outcomes, influencing career opportunities, social mobility, and overall well-being (Outhwaite et al., 2022). However, challenges in mathematical attainment often emerge during the early years of school, with significant implications for later development. In the UK, approximately 20% of children fail to meet the expected standard in mathematics by the age of 5, a trend that persists into later childhood, with similar rates of underachievement reported by age 11 (Department for Education, 2017). This early underperformance has profound consequences. Research suggests that children who begin school with low mathematical skills are more likely to struggle academically throughout their education, creating disparities that widen over time (Aubrey et al., 2006). Given that early difficulties in mathematics often persist and widen over time, there is a critical need for early, non-invasive screening measures, such as the Order Processing Questionnaire (O'Connor et al., 2018) that can flag children who may struggle. The OPQ is designed to address this gap by capturing everyday ordering skills that are closely linked to early mathematical development. By addressing these difficulties during critical developmental periods, educators and policymakers can enhance not only mathematical skills but also broader educational equity and societal outcomes.

A growing body of work shows that both numerical (e.g., Lyons et al., 2016; Sasanguie & Vos, 2018) and non-numerical ordering skills (e.g., Attout et al., 2014; Morsanyi et al., 2018, 2024; O'Connor et al., 2018) are reliable predictors of later mathematical achievement, highlighting the role of ordering skills as a key cognitive foundation for early mathematics development. However, the role of non-numerical ordering skills in mathematical development has been under-researched in comparison to that of numerical ordering. In the current study, we focused on assessing the psychometric properties of the parental Order-Processing Questionnaire (OPQ; O'Connor et al., 2018), a measure developed to assess children's ability to engage in tasks, which have a strong ordering component to them, as this measure may act as an indicator of early mathematical difficulties in children at the beginning of primary school, helping to identify those children who could benefit from early intervention. The OPQ was developed to assess children's everyday ordering abilities, providing a novel parental-report measure that does not directly involve numerical processing. This approach represents an innovative method for identifying children at risk of mathematical difficulties by focusing on broader cognitive abilities linked to ordering which may, in turn, have implications for the later development of symbolic number knowledge. The OPQ was inspired by clinical observations and research highlighting the difficulties faced by children with developmental dyscalculia (DD), such as challenges in sequencing tasks or understanding temporal and spatial order (National Centre for Learning Difficulties, 2007).

Only three studies have investigated the extent to which the OPQ is a predictor of mathematical achievement. In a longitudinal study examining the development of numerical skills in the first two years of primary school, O'Connor et al. (2018) administered the OPQ to parents of children in their first year. The study also assessed children's numerical and non-numerical ordering skills, as well as traditional math tasks (e.g., approximate addition, counting, number line estimation), and measured mathematical achievement at the end of the first and second years. OPQ scores, measured only at the start of the first year, predicted both later mathematical performance and growth over the two-year period, even when controlling for approximate estimation skills. These results highlight the importance of everyday ordering abilities in shaping early numerical development.

Building on this, a 7-item, age-appropriate version of the OPQ was developed for children aged 8–11 (Morsanyi et al., 2018). Comparing children with Developmental Dyscalculia (DD) to matched controls, parents of children with DD reported significantly poorer everyday ordering skills. OPQ scores, along with order working memory and number line performance, were significant predictors of group membership, with OPQ scores being the strongest predictor. Further evidence suggests the OPQ's predictive power extends beyond numerical contexts: in 8–11-year-olds, OPQ scores significantly predicted both mathematics and reading achievement, even after controlling for vocabulary, working memory, and age (Morsanyi et al., 2020). This indicates that everyday ordering skills reflect broader cognitive processes supporting academic success across domains. Together, these findings highlight the OPQ's potential as a practical, non-invasive tool for identifying children at risk of mathematical difficulties.

Despite these findings, the psychometric properties of the OPQ remain underexplored. The present study therefore aimed to evaluate its factor structure using confirmatory factor analysis (CFA). In their initial development of the OPQ, O'Connor et al. (2018) employed a Principal Components Analysis with Varimax rotation, to uncover a two-factor model. This model differentiated between positively and negatively worded items in the questionnaire and demonstrated adequate internal consistency. However, while these findings were encouraging, the stability of this factor structure has not been rigorously tested in subsequent studies involving larger samples. To address this gap, the current study applied Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) to evaluate the two-factor structure of the OPQ in a larger sample of parents with young children, with a larger sample size than in O'Connor et al. (2018). A successful replication of the two-factor model would significantly enhance the OPQ's credibility as a reliable measure for identifying children at risk of mathematical difficulties. Conversely, if the CFA results reveal that the two-factor structure does not provide an adequate fit, this would indicate the need for further refinement of the measure. This could involve re-examining the theoretical underpinnings of the factors, adjusting item wording, or considering alternative factor structures. By addressing these challenges, the OPQ could be developed into a robust and reliable marker of poor mathematical skills, supporting efforts to improve educational outcomes for children in the early years of primary school.

METHODS

Design

A cross-sectional survey was used in the study. Data collection took place online using the Qualtrics platform, and participants completed the questionnaire on their own electronic devices. Inclusion criteria specified that participants must be parents or primary caregivers of children in their first year of primary school (equivalent to age 4–5 years in Northern Ireland) and that respondents themselves were aged 18 years or older. This ensured that participants were legally able to provide informed consent and had direct knowledge of their child's behaviours. Data collection was fully anonymised, and no personally identifiable information was obtained beyond basic demographic details. Prior to commencement, ethical approval for the study was granted by the institutional research ethics committee of the first author's university. The research adhered to the British Psychological Society's Code of Human Research Ethics, ensuring compliance with ethical standards relating to informed consent, confidentiality, voluntary participation, and the right to withdraw.

Participants

The parents of 509 children, in their first year of primary school, were recruited via several schools across Northern Ireland. They provided data on their child's age and gender (253 females, Mean age = 56.59 months, SD = 3.82 months). Due to the demographics of Northern Ireland, the majority of the sample (96%) were white. Recruitment was conducted through several primary schools across Northern Ireland. Schools were approached and asked to share information about the study via their websites, newsletters, and social media platforms. Participation was entirely voluntary, and no financial incentives were offered, although parents were informed of the potential educational and developmental relevance of the research. This sample size exceeded the minimum recommendations for conducting confirmatory factor analysis (CFA), which typically require at least 200 participants or a ratio of 10–20 participants per estimated parameter, thereby ensuring adequate statistical power for the analyses.

Materials

Parental Order Processing Questionnaire (OPQ; O'Connor et al., 2018). The OPQ is an 8-item parental report measure designed to assess children's everyday ordering skills, which are theorised to underpin early mathematical development. Items capture routine, real-world tasks that require ordering abilities, such as sequencing events, understanding temporal relationships, and organising steps to complete tasks (e.g., "My son/daughter understands how the seasons of the year follow each other"). Responses are provided on a 7-point Likert scale ranging from 1 = strongly disagree to 7 =

strongly agree. Three items are reverse scored to control for parents succumbing to acquiescence bias when completing the questionnaire, and therefore encourage more thoughtful responses. Higher scores indicate stronger perceived ordering abilities. In the present study, internal consistency was assessed using Cronbach's alpha, yielding an overall reliability coefficient of $\alpha = .76$, indicating acceptable internal consistency for research purposes. As previously mentioned, the OPQ has been previously used in studies examining its association with early mathematics performance (Morsanyi et al., 2018; Morsanyi et al., 2020; O'Connor et al., 2018), and has been found to correlate with mathematical performance in children.

Procedure

Data collection was conducted entirely online. The research team contacted headteachers and administrative staff in primary schools across Northern Ireland, inviting them to share details of the study with parents via established communication channels such as school websites, newsletters, and social media pages. Parents who were interested in participating accessed the survey link, which directed them to a detailed information sheet outlining the study aims, procedures, inclusion criteria, and ethical safeguards. After reading this information, parents provided informed consent electronically before proceeding.

Once consent was obtained, parents were first asked to complete demographic questions regarding their child's age, gender, and ethnicity. They then completed the OPQ, rating each of the eight items based on their observations of their child's typical behaviour in everyday contexts. On average, participation took approximately 5–10 minutes to complete. Upon submission, parents were automatically presented with a debrief sheet reiterating the purpose of the study, explaining how their data would be used, and providing contact details for the research team in case of queries. Participants were also thanked for their involvement and informed of the potential implications of the research for early educational screening and intervention.

RESULTS

Descriptive statistics for each item in the OPQ are shown in Table 1. The average scores for each of the OPQ items indicate that, on average, parents agreed to a reasonable extent that their children were able to carry out everyday tasks which involved using ordering skills.

Table 1

Table showing descriptive statistics for the OPQ

Item	Mean	SD
Understands how the seasons of the year follow each other	4.36	1.90
Can easily recall the order in which past events happened	5.08	1.80
Is able to plan a sequence of activities independently	5.20	1.77
Would be able to recall the order of typical daily events	5.70	1.64
Understands that some things always have to be done in a particular order	6.02	1.50
Is easily confused by changes in routine ^a	5.20	1.68
Finds it difficult to learn new activities which involve a sequence of actions that have to be performed in a particular order ^a	5.33	1.72
Finds it difficult to understand how the days of the week follow each other ^a	4.79	1.90

^a Reverse-scored item

A confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was conducted to evaluate the same two-factor model of the OPQ found by O'Connor et al. (2018), with the five positively worded items assigned to the "Positive Item" factor and the three negatively worded items assigned to the "Negative Item" factor. The analysis included data from all 509 participants, with no missing data. The CFA was performed using R statistical software with the Lavaan package (Rosseel, 2012), a widely used tool for structural

equation modelling. The analysis employed Robust Maximum Likelihood (MLR) estimation. This method provides robust standard errors and adjusts the chi-square statistic using the Satorra-Bentler correction (Bentler, 1995), which accounts for violations of the normality assumption. We selected Robust Maximum Likelihood (MLR) estimation because our data were ordinal and showed evidence of non-normality. Unlike conventional maximum likelihood estimation, which assumes multivariate normality, MLR adjusts standard errors and fit statistics (using the Satorra-Bentler correction) to provide more accurate parameter estimates under such conditions. Alternative estimation methods (e.g., Weighted Least Squares Mean and Variance adjusted, WLSMV) were considered, but MLR was chosen as it is less sensitive to sample size imbalance and allows for the use of robust fit indices across a range of model complexities.

Several goodness-of-fit indices were calculated to evaluate the model. These included the Satorra-Bentler corrected χ^2 test, the χ^2/DF ratio, the robust Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA), the robust Comparative Fit Index (CFI), the robust Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI), and the robust Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR). Together, these indices provided a comprehensive assessment of the model's fit to the data.

The measures of absolute fit for the two-factor model of the OPQ yielded mixed results. The Satorra-Bentler corrected χ^2 test was significant, indicating a discrepancy between the sample covariance matrix and the model's estimated covariance matrix. This suggests that the model did not perfectly fit the data. The χ^2/df ratio, another commonly used measure of absolute fit, is generally considered acceptable when the value is less than 3 (Kline, 2005). However, as presented in Table 2, the χ^2/df ratio exceeded this threshold, suggesting the model may not meet conventional standards for good fit. It is important to note that chi-square-based indices are sensitive to sample size, with larger samples increasing the likelihood of detecting statistically significant discrepancies even when the model fits reasonably well, therefore some researchers propose a more lenient threshold of 5 for the χ^2/df ratio, under which the current data would demonstrate a reasonable fit under these guidelines (Marsh & Hocevar, 1985). The SRMR, another measure of absolute fit, produced a value below .08, meeting the criterion for good fit (Hu & Bentler, 1999). The RMSEA, which accounts for model complexity, yielded a value indicative of poor fit as it exceeded .08 (MacCallum et al., 1996). This discrepancy highlights the mixed nature of the absolute fit indices for the two-factor model. The model performed more favourably in terms of comparative fit indices. Both the CFI and TLI approached or exceeded the threshold of .90, indicating an adequate fit (University of California, Los Angeles, n.d.). These indices suggest that the two-factor structure aligns reasonably well with the observed data despite the shortcomings identified by other fit measures. Overall, the fit indices collectively provide partial support for the original two-factor structure found by O'Connor et al. (2018).

Table 2
 Goodness-of-fit statistics for the two-factor model of the OPQ

	χ^2	df	<i>p</i>	χ^2/df	CFI	TLI	RMSEA [90% CI]	SRMR
Two-factor Model	72.54	9	< .001	3.82	.92	.88	.08 [.084 – .105]	.05

The factor loadings, error variances, and factor covariances for the two-factor model of the OPQ are presented in Figure 1. The factor loadings ranged from .48 to .75, indicating moderate to strong contributions of individual items to their respective underlying factors. These results suggest that the items generally align well with the proposed two-factor structure, providing evidence of the model's theoretical soundness. The reliability of the factors was assessed using Cronbach's alpha. The Positive Item factor demonstrated acceptable internal consistency ($\alpha = .79$), reflecting sufficient reliability for

the items within this factor. However, the Negative Item factor exhibited a lower reliability score ($\alpha = .53$). This discrepancy is likely influenced by the smaller number of items (three) assigned to the Negative Item factor compared to the Positive Item factor (five), which inherently limits the variance captured and reduces the reliability of the measure. Convergent and discriminant validity were further evaluated through the calculation of Average Variance Extracted (AVE). The Positive Item factor demonstrated an AVE of .44, which, while below the .50 threshold for strong convergent validity (Fornell & Larcker, 1981), still exceeded the squared inter-factor correlation ($r^2 = .31$), indicating discriminant validity. In contrast, the Negative Item factor had an AVE of .27, suggesting weaker convergent validity. These findings underscore the need for further refinement, particularly in the Negative Item factor, to strengthen its validity. Modification indices suggested potential model improvements, such as allowing covariance between certain items (e.g., between Q6 and Q7, Q2 and Q3, Q3 and Q8, and Q7 and Q8) and reassigning Q2 to the Negative Item factor. While modification indices suggested that allowing certain error covariances could improve model fit, these adjustments would substantially alter the theoretical basis of the OPQ. Correlating items would risk capitalising on sample-specific noise rather than reflecting meaningful constructs. In line with best practices in structural equation modelling, we prioritised theoretical interpretability and model parsimony over statistical optimisation. Retaining the original two-factor structure ensures that subsequent refinement of the OPQ builds on a theoretically coherent foundation, rather than an empirically over-fitted solution. Overall, while the factor loadings and reliability metrics provide partial support for the two-factor structure, the weaker performance of the Negative Item factor highlights areas requiring further development. These include addressing the imbalance in item distribution and exploring strategies to enhance the validity and reliability of the Negative Item factor. Future studies should aim to refine the questionnaire to ensure it better captures the constructs it is intended to measure while maintaining theoretical coherence.

Figure 1 shows a path diagram presents the factor loadings, error variances, and factor covariances for the two-factor OPQ model. Factor loadings (shown on the arrows from factors to items) indicate how strongly each questionnaire item reflects its underlying factor. Error variances (shown next to items) represent variance in responses not explained by the factor. The covariance between factors (shown by the curved arrow) reflects the degree of shared variance between the Positive and Negative Item factors.

Figure 1

Path diagram with factor loadings and error variances for the two-factor OPQ model

* $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$; *** $p < .001$

DISCUSSION

The findings of the current study provide partial validation for the original two-factor structure of the OPQ proposed by O'Connor et al. (2018). While the confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) yielded some support for the model, the fit indices presented a mixed picture. Although some fit indices (SRMR and CFI), suggested adequate fit, others (RMSEA, χ^2), indicated poor fit. The issues with fit indices suggest that further exploration of the factor structure may be necessary. Reliability and validity statistics were stronger for the Positive Item factor compared to the Negative Item factor. This disparity may be partially attributed to the smaller number of items within the Negative Item factor, which could affect its reliability and overall contribution to the model. Despite these challenges, the items demonstrated moderate to strong factor loadings, although there are areas requiring refinement to enhance the practical application OPQ.

The findings of the present study provide partial support for previous research on the Order-Processing Questionnaire (OPQ) and its underlying structure. Consistent with O'Connor et al. (2018), our results somewhat support the proposed two-factor model, with items loading appropriately onto positive and negative factors and moderate-to-strong factor loadings indicating theoretical coherence. This aligns with earlier evidence highlighting the OPQ's potential as a useful measure of everyday ordering skills, which has previously been linked to early mathematical development (Morsanyi et al., 2018; O'Connor et al., 2018). The findings of this study carry important implications for how the OPQ might be further developed. Despite its promise, the mixed results regarding fit indices, reliability, and validity highlight the need for further refinement of the questionnaire to improve its accuracy and practical applicability. Enhancing the OPQ's reliability and validity will be essential to ensuring it functions effectively as a potential tool for early identification and intervention. To strengthen its utility, future research should focus on two key areas: validating the underlying factor structure and evaluating the predictive validity of the OPQ against mathematical performance.

First, although the confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) provided partial support for the two-factor structure of the OPQ, mixed model fit indices and the low reliability of the Negative Item factor suggest that the factor structure may be driven more by item valence than by underlying theoretical constructs which play an important role in everyday ordering skills. This raises the possibility that a unidimensional model may better capture everyday ordering abilities. To examine whether the two-factor solution reflects substantive constructs or merely item valence, future research should directly compare the two-factor model with a unidimensional model in which all items load on a single everyday ordering factor. Such comparisons could be conducted using CFA model fit indices, chi-square difference testing, or information criteria (e.g., AIC, BIC). In addition, exploratory structural equation modelling (ESEM) or bifactor models could be employed to assess whether item valence contributes systematically to variance beyond a general ordering factor. This would provide a stronger empirical basis for determining whether a unidimensional structure more accurately captures everyday ordering skills. Such work would clarify the dimensionality of everyday ordering skills and enhance the measure's reliability and construct validity.

Whilst prior research suggests that everyday ordering skills are linked to early mathematics achievement, the current study did not include concurrent or longitudinal measures of mathematical performance in order to assess the predictive validity of the OPQ and, therefore, we are unable to make any strong claims concerning the screening potential of the OPQ in relation to early mathematical difficulties. Additional studies are needed to comprehensively evaluate its effectiveness across a broader range of mathematical outcomes. These should include both objective measures (e.g., standardized test scores) and subjective metrics (e.g., parental and/or teacher ratings of math skills, self-perceptions of maths skills) to provide a more nuanced understanding of the OPQ's predictive power. Future work should incorporate subjective and objective assessments to examine the extent to which OPQ scores predict later achievement or identify children at risk of mathematical difficulties. Teacher ratings could capture children's behaviours in structured learning environments, while direct behavioural tasks (e.g., standardized mathematics assessments administered in school) could provide objective measures. Combining these approaches with parental reports of their child's maths skills (see Lin et al., 2021) would enable cross-informant validation, reduce rater-specific bias, and clarify whether the OPQ predicts performance across both home and school contexts (Relojo-Howell, 2024). Such triangulation would significantly strengthen the questionnaire's validity. By addressing these areas, the OPQ could be developed into a more robust and reliable measure. This would enhance its potential to support early detection of children at risk for mathematical difficulties, ultimately enabling timely interventions that improve educational outcomes and mitigate long-term challenges.

A key limitation of the study is that the OPQ is reliant on parental reports on a Likert scale to assess children's everyday ordering abilities. While parents provide valuable insight into their child's behaviour and skills, their assessments are inherently subjective and may be prone to bias. For example, a parent who is highly engaged in their child's educational activities may rate the child's abilities more positively than a less-involved parent, regardless of the child's actual skill level. Additionally, parents may not have observed their child in contexts where ordering abilities are most evident, such as classroom settings or social interactions, further limiting the comprehensiveness of their responses. Future research could also incorporate reports from other sources (e.g., teachers), who observe the child in diverse settings and may offer a more balanced perspective. Including multi-informant data, such as teacher reports and direct child assessments of ordering skills, would provide convergent evidence and reduce potential bias associated with parental ratings alone. By refining the OPQ and establishing its predictive utility, future research could produce a theoretically grounded and practical instrument for use in educational and developmental contexts. This would not only strengthen understanding of the role of everyday ordering in early cognitive development but also support early identification and targeted intervention for children who may struggle with mathematics, ultimately improving educational outcomes during a critical stage of learning.

A further limitation of the current study is that we did not include any measure of socioeconomic status (SES), meaning its potential influence on everyday ordering skills could not be examined, and we could not ascertain the SES background of participants in the study. SES is a well established

predictor of math performance, with meta-analytic evidence showing moderate positive correlations between family SES and academic outcomes (Sirin, 2005). Early SES disparities also manifest strongly in foundational informal math skills such as number acuity, counting principles, and number ordering, that serve as the basis for ordering tasks (Jordan et al., 2006; Jordan et al., 2007). These foundational differences are significant mediators of later mathematics success, especially among children from lower-SES backgrounds. Without SES data, unmeasured SES-related effects may account for some of the individual differences observed in ordering skills, thereby limiting both the internal validity and interpretability of our results. In future research, this limitation could be addressed by including a validated measure of SES such as parental education level, household income, or eligibility for free school meals, which are commonly used proxies in educational research (Sirin, 2005). Collecting these data would allow for statistical control of SES effects when examining relationships between ordering skills and mathematical achievement, thereby improving the internal validity of findings. Additionally, incorporating SES as a covariate could help to clarify whether the observed associations differ across socioeconomic groups, offering a more nuanced understanding of how environmental factors influence early cognitive and mathematical development.

CONCLUSION

This study provides partial validation for the two-factor structure of the OPQ as originally proposed by O'Connor et al. (2018). The findings confirm the potential of the OPQ as a tool for measuring everyday ordering skills, but there are still some issues with the reliability and validity of the questionnaire in its current form, which hamper its potential as a screening tool for early mathematical difficulties. The Positive Item factor, in particular, showed stronger reliability and validity, indicating its potential as a marker of early risk. Although the Negative Item factor requires refinement, the OPQ as a whole provides a promising framework for identifying children who may benefit from early intervention. Conceptually, we propose that OPQ factors map onto ordering-related cognitive processes, which in turn scaffold the acquisition of symbolic number skills and broader mathematical achievement. Future studies should test this model explicitly by linking OPQ performance with subjective reports of mathematical skills from parents and teachers, as well as objective measures of mathematical skills from children directly, to gain a more nuanced understanding of whether the OPQ is indeed a viable tool for detecting early mathematics difficulties.

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